

Colorimetric determination of ascorbic acid in pharmaceuticals using U^{VI}-4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol complex

S. P. Arya* and P. Jain

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-136 119, India

E-mail : chem@granth.kuk.ernet.in Fax : 91-01744-20277/20198/21639

Manuscript received 1 November 2000, revised 16 May 2001, accepted 19 May 2001

An analytical procedure based on the proportionate decrease in the color intensity of U^{VI}-4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol complex with the increasing amount of vitamin C is described. The complex shows λ_{\max} at 530 nm. Beer's law holds well in the range 2–16 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The applicability of the method is tested by analyzing pure vitamin C solutions and multivitamin pharmaceuticals.

Different redox couples such as Fe^{III}-Fe^{II}, V^V-V^{IV}, Cu^{II}-Cu^I and Cr^{VI}-Cr^{III} have been used for the determination of ascorbic acid¹. A simple and rapid method based on a proportionate decrease observed in the color intensity of U^{VI}-4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol complex by the addition of ascorbic acid is proposed here which involves the extraction of U^{VI}-PAR complex into *n*-butanol.

Results and Discussion

Uranium(vi) is known to form a red colored complex with 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol in neutral or slightly acidic solutions². Preliminary investigations revealed a linear relationship between the decrease in color intensity of U^{VI}-PAR complex by the addition of increasing amount of ascorbic acid.

The reagent blank absorbs strongly at 400 nm but its absorbance decreases along with the increasing wavelength and becomes very small at 530 nm or above. The complex shows a broad absorption band at 530 nm where absorbance measurements were carried out.

The different factors affecting the extraction and absorbance of the complex were studied. In the study, 10 ml of aqueous phase containing 100 $\mu\text{g U}^{\text{VI}}$ was used. The aqueous phase containing the U^{VI}-PAR complex was equilibrated with *n*-butanol (2 × 10 ml). The optimum conditions found are : 0.6–1.0 ml of PAR aqueous solution (0.1%); waiting time for reduction, 1 min; equilibrium time, 0.5–10 min. The complex showed maximum absorbance when extracted in the pH range 5.80–7.15. A change of pH on either side of this range shows gradual decrease in absorbance.

The extraction behavior of the complex was tested into different solvents. The complex could be extracted into oxygenated solvents such as *n*-butanol, isoamyl alcohol, ethyl acetate and methyl isobutyl ketone, the extraction

decreasing in that order. The solvents like chloroform, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, dichloromethane and *n*-hexane did not extract the complex.

Table 1. Effect of different substances in the determination of 200 μg of ascorbic acid

Substance added ^a	Tolerance limit (mg/25 ml)	Error (%)
Sugars :		
Sucrose, maltose	200.0	-1.5
Glucose, xylose, lactose	100.0	-
Fructose, mannose	50.0	-
Starch	10.0	-
Organic acids ^b :		
Maleic acid	5.0	-
Tartaric acid	1.0	-
Trichloroacetic acid, succinic acid	0.5	+1.2
Benzoic acid, salicylic acid	0.5	-, +1.6
Metal ions :		
Mg ^{II} , Ca ^{II}	5.0	-
La ^{III}	0.05	-
Mo ^{VI}	0.01	-
Vitamins and amino acids :		
Nicotinamide, methionine	2.0	-
Glutathione	1.0	-
Folic acid	0.5	-
Vit. B ₁ , B ₂ , B ₆ , B ₁₂	0.5	-
Glutamic acid, aspartic acid	0.2	-
Vit. B ₅ , cysteine	0.1	-
Miscellaneous :		
Glycerol, acetone	500.0	+1.2
Methanol, formaldehyde	200.0	-
Chloride, sulfate	200.0	-
Thiourea, urea	100.0	-
Fluoride	30.0	-
Thiosulfate	0.2	-

^aSubstances were added prior to addition of ascorbic acid.

^bOptimum pH was adjusted in each case.

Under optimum conditions, Beer's law plot constructed at 530 nm showed a linear relationship between the absorbance and concentration of ascorbic acid in the range 2–16 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The absorbance of the complex remained unchanged for at least 24 h. The calculated molar absorptivity

and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $2.3 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.013 \text{ } \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The reproducibility of method was checked by making five replicate determination with $200 \text{ } \mu\text{g}$ of ascorbic acid giving 0.018 as standard deviation.

The studies related to the effect of possible ingredients associated with vitamin C preparation were carried out and their results are shown in Table 1. A deviation of $\pm 2.0\%$ in absorbance was taken as the criterion for determining the tolerance limit in each case. The tolerance level for sugars is relatively high as compared to the tolerances for organic acids, vitamins and amino acids.

The applicability of the proposed method was tested by the assay of vitamin C tablets and capsules (Limcee, Celin Chewcee, Cebexin, Becozym forte etc) with satisfactory results. The results were in agreement with the reported values. Though the method is not sufficiently sensitive, yet it is simple and rapid as the single determination takes hardly 6–7 min once sample solution is ready for analysis.

Experimental

A Hitachi-Shimadzu UV-140-02 spectrophotometer having matched 1-cm quartz cells was used for making absorbance measurements. Ascorbic acid solution was prepared afresh ($100 \text{ } \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$).

Procedure : To the $100 \text{ } \mu\text{g}$ of uranium(vi) solution, an aliquot of ascorbic acid sample solution was added. The

contents were swirled and waited for 1 min followed by the addition of PAR solution (0.6 ml). The aqueous phase volume was made to 10 ml with water and the colored complex was extracted with *n*-butanol ($2 \times 10 \text{ ml}$) for 30 s. The combined extract was treated with anhydrous sodium sulfate to remove the entrained water and then the volume was made up to 25 ml with *n*-butanol. The absorbance of the red complex was measured at 530 nm against the reagent blank. The amount of ascorbic acid was assessed from the standard calibration curve prepared by taking different amounts of ascorbic acid up to $16 \text{ } \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

A known weight of the powder obtained from 5–10 tablets/capsules equivalent to 1 mg ml^{-1} of ascorbic acid, was dissolved in water. A $100 \text{ } \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ solution was obtained by suitable dilution of the stock solution. The diluted solution was analyzed with the proposed method.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank the Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, for facilities. One of the authors (P.J.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. S. P. Arya, M. Mahajan and P. Jain, *Anal. Sci.*, 1998, **14**, 889.
2. A. I. Busev and V. M. Ivanov, *Vestnik Moskov. Univ., Ser. Khim.*, 1960, **15**, 3.